

Quality Management Principles as Correlates of Teachers' Job Performance in Unity Schools in South-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated quality management principles as correlates of teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. The study was guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 1,572 teachers in unity schools South-East, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 472 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two sets of instruments titled "Quality Management Principles Questionnaire, (QMPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire, (JJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts made up of two specialists in Educational Management and a specialist in Measurement and Evaluation all from Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Cronbach Alpha which was used for test of the internal consistency of the instruments yielded overall coefficient of 0.87 and 0.91 for QMPQ and TJPQ respectively. The researcher together with six research assistants administered copies of the questionnaires to the respondents through a direct approach. A total of 472 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 458 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 97% return rate. Data collected was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and simple regression to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study revealed among others that there is substantial positive and significant relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. It was also found that there is a very high positive and significant relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Unity school principals should constitute committee saddled with the responsibility of monitoring and ensuring constantly focus on learning process to improve the job performance of teachers.

Keywords: Quality Management, Quality Management, Learning Process, Staff Development, Teamwork, Teachers, Job Performance

Introduction

Education is a productive vehicle for economic, socio-cultural and political development of nations and individuals. Adinna and Okafor (2023) opined that education is a process of acquiring skills, obtaining relevant knowledge and aptitudes in order to survive in the society. It is universally recognized as an instrument for equipping individuals with functional knowledge and skill to build up their character, attitude and vision (Okafor & Egwu, 2022). Education, in this perspective is perceived as a cornerstone of economic growth and societal development, and a principal means of improving the welfare of individual. Okafor and Enemuo (2022) asserted that education is one the ways of equipping individuals with needed skills and knowledge for productive activities in the society. The Federal Government of Nigeria has adopted education as an instrument for affecting national development and social change (Federal Republic of Nigeria [FRN], 2013). To achieve this goal, FRN (2013) emphasized that quality education should be given at all levels of education. A comprehensive view into the Nigerian educational system shows that, it is systematically structured into pre-primary, basic, secondary and tertiary education. Secondary school education refers to post-primary formal education offered to students who have successfully completed their primary school education.

The secondary school education is not only designed to provide sound and responsible secondary school graduates for low level employment; but also to deposit in students' quality education potentials to succeed in life upon graduation; if they cannot afford tertiary education. No Wonder, Newman (2012) opined that the secondary school education has always played an indispensable role in shaping the economic realities of any society. Secondary education has continued to be important, and this is why there has been a growing concern about the quality of education that is offered in that level of education. The quality of secondary education is a crucial issue that affects the development of individuals, communities, and nations (Okafor & Enemuo, 2024). In fact, attainment of the primary objectives of secondary education demands that quality be built into the system. Adinna and Okafor (2023) maintained that secondary Education is the gateway to tertiary education and essentially provides greater number of lower level manpower needed for proper economic growth and national development. Consequently, all efforts must be directed towards improving teachers' productivity in secondary schools.

Teachers are employees who implement the educational policies of the state in the light of the country's goals and objectives. Nwite (2016) viewed teachers as people that coordinate all the factors in teaching and learning process to promote the attainment of educational objectives.

However, the success of any educational institution depends to a great extent on teachers' productivity. Okonkwo (2013) observed that teacher's interactions, views, duties and behavior, play crucial role in ensuring advancement in education institutions. This crucial role teacher play makes their productivity essential. To successfully carryout the roles associated with the teaching profession, the teacher needs to have positive attitude and be committed to the school as an organization. This implies that the achievement of school goals and objectives depends to a great extent on teachers' job performance.

The concept of teachers' job performance refers to the actions teachers perform in schools in order to achieve education goals. It involves all the actions and processes through which schools can raise the standard of instruction the students receive, as well as the general achievement in the school. Since quality has become an important issue in organizational performance, teachers' job performance has also become an essential factor in secondary school administration. Teachers' job performance is concerned with the overall effectiveness and efficiency of getting things done in the school organization. It is essentially a measure of how well the school organization converts its resources (students) into finished products (quality graduates). Teachers' job performance according to Guillermo (2018), refers to the duties performed by teachers at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. It could be measured through teachers' satisfaction and job attitudes such as job commitment, feelings of job challenge, job meaningfulness and job responsibility (Guillermo, 2018)

However, it appears that the rate of getting things done by teachers is not as effective and efficient as expected. The economic situation of Nigeria has forced teachers to combine other businesses with teaching, thus affecting their performance in the school (Oluwaseun, 2016). Some teachers who would have been very productive in the school seem to be distracted by other businesses they engage in, which in turn consume most of their official times. Ighor (2014) in her study on education and teachers' job performance, found that teachers' job performance is determined by effective teaching; measured by students' academic performance in examinations; punctuality at school and classes, giving extra lessons to students; and contribution to the progress of the school through participation in co-curricular activities such as sports, debating, dancing, students' discipline, committee assignment as may be assigned by the principal. The scholar further stressed that if teachers fail to measure up in these various assignments, they may be perceived uncooperative and unproductive.

Unfortunately, evidences from research revealed that there is a problem with the leadership provided by principals in secondary schools in Nigeria. In different reports, principals are indicted by stakeholders for inefficiency and failure to provide quality management in their schools, which in turn has resulted to poor quality inputs and outputs. Alimi et al. (2011) alleged that there is an outcry on accountability, because principals' authority as administrative, technical, and pedagogical heads of secondary schools has become a matter of serious concern. Akpan (2011)

also recorded that stakeholders attributed the falling standard in secondary school education to inefficiency of principals in managing the schools. Backstrom et al (as cited in Fundin et al., 2017) concluded that one major problem which the entire Nigerian educational system has continued to grapple with is that of organization and effective management which have continued to serve as an albatross to educational development.

Quality management according to Nawela et al. (2015) is a management approach that was introduced by Professor W. Edwards Deming in the 1950s to seek sources of continuous improvement to provide quality product and services to customers or clients. In the concept of quality management, the word “Quality” is particularly important. Quality has been used synonymously with excellence, goodness, efficiency or appropriateness in different places. It has been used to describe something that conforms to a special specified standard or requirement. It is in line with this that quality management was defined by Oluwuo et al. (as cited in Onyeike, 2016) as an art of managing the resources to achieve excellence. Comparably, Suleman (2015) referred to it as being concerned with managing the whole organization so that excellence is achieved in all dimensions of products and services that are important to customers. Quality management was also defined by Stoner (2012) as a management approach that is based on participation of all members of the organization and aims at long term profitability through customer satisfaction, benefits to members, stakeholders and society. From the forgoing, it can be deduced that quality management is a customer focused management system that involves all employees in continuous improvement of different aspect of an organization. The concept defines a participative management system that places high premium on quality. It is a holistic approach to management which affects every aspect of an organization with a view to building quality into it.

Quality management in education has to do with all the processes that ensure continuous improvement for all the stakeholders involved in the school system. It is the development and execution of programmes that guide the activities of an organization for continuous improvement of staff performance (Radoica, 2015). Quality management involves excellently organizing the activities of the school with the view to enhancing the reliability and effectiveness of its performance (Devos et al., 2014). The goal of quality management is to harmonize educational activities in such a manner that not only do teachers approach their designed task with passion, but are also interested in improving the way the job is performed. Asogwa et al. (2018) revealed that quality management is characterized by several principles. According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO, 2018), quality management is made up of seven principles. These principles include; customer focus, leadership, involvement of people, process approach, system approach to management, continuous improvement and factual approach to decision making.

In the secondary school system, quality management emphasizes continuous improvement in all functional areas and activities of the school. It however, requires the school principal who is

responsible for leadership to initiate its strategies and also ensure total support for application. Despite the fact that the principles of quality management that are recorded in literature are numerous, Kalpana (2014) singled out the following as being ideal for improving teachers' job performance: focus on learning process, non-threatening assessment; staff development; teamwork; decentralized management; and community involvement or participation. In this study, five out of the six mentioned variables by Kalpana are adopted as Quality Management principles that could be applied by principals for improving teachers' quality in federal government secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria. The variables adopted include: focus on learning process, staff development, teamwork, decentralized management and community involvement. According to Kalpana (2014), the central element of the school functioning is what happens in the classroom, and that is why the interaction between the teacher and the learner remains the most direct predictor of a school's quality. Kalpana maintained that this ultimately requires a commitment to the learning process and an obligation by the school principal to ensure that teachers employ the most appropriate pedagogic practices. Invariably, focus on learning process connotes paying adequate attention to students' learning by the principal as the instructional leader of the school. It involves focusing on the learning process, the quality of learning and the way it is delivered. Since teachers' job performance is measured with students' achievement and academic performance in both internal and external examination, it is pertinent that principal as the administrative head of the secondary school pays adequate attention to the quality of instruction students receive. Focus on learning process is a key factor for improving students' academic performance and teachers' job performance. Another group of principles that contribute to quality in the learning process of students and teachers' job performance is staff development principle.

Staff development involves all processes geared towards improving the ability of teachers in the performance of their job in terms of knowledge, skills, competencies, attitudes and professional growth. In quality management framework, teachers are viewed as indispensable resources that must be continuously enhanced and empowered using various developmental programmes and other motivational measures. Admittedly, Njeru (2011) confirmed that quality management advocates for continuous training of teachers until they achieve as much as they can within the limits of the system in which they operate. This is because when institutions develop their teachers, they enhance their skills, competencies and overall performance, and in return the institutions benefit from their empowerment. Rivers (2017) posited that staff development aids ongoing skill development, understanding of the most recent technological developments, and assisting staff in becoming comfortable with technology and realizing their full potentials. The scholar concluded that continuous staff development forces teachers to be proactive and forward thinking in order to attract and retain good employees and improves school's reputation. However, development programmes should also include training teachers in the methods of quality

management. In order to ensure sustainable staff development programmes in secondary schools, it is important that teachers are encouraged to work as a team.

Teamwork is important for providing a quality work environment that encourages strong staff commitment to continuous improvement of the school system. Teamwork refers to the collective efforts of individuals towards the actualization of a common vision or goal. Teamwork is opposed to one-man affair but collective collaboration that is found on the abilities of different individuals. Ndu (2013) confirmed this idea by stating that a successful school requires more than just individual efforts but teamwork to accomplish the many tasks involved in teaching all subjects and in guiding students into acceptable behaviour. The teamwork approach to management offers one a way of achieving a coherent strategy for promoting teachers' job performance. Teamwork emphasized collaboration, solidarity and interdependence. Werner and Desimone (2012) stated that teamwork is a process where work is performed by a team to achieve a common goal. They further maintained that teamwork plays a key role in the effort to improve outcome as it influences the level of motivation of teachers and helps to create a friendly school climate and environment; that promotes productivity. Quality management is a management philosophy that believes and values team result more than individual results because, with team result there is a boost to employee morale as employees pride themselves in their teams' successes or achievements. Therefore, teamwork remains an important aspect of quality even in school settings. Similarly, decentralized management is another quality management principle in education. It is against this foregoing background that the researcher conceived the idea to investigate quality management principles as correlates of teachers' job performance in federal government secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Secondary school education in Nigeria is designed not only to provide sound and responsible secondary school graduates for low level employment but also to deposit in students' quality education potentials to succeed upon graduation. Regrettably, observation has shown that most secondary school students in Nigeria turn-out as half-baked graduates; who lack fundamental competencies for work. Many times, they do not meet the satisfaction of employers of labour, the stakeholders and the community at large. This problem is believed to have contributed to the high rate of unemployment and underemployment among secondary school graduates since a reasonable percentage of them comes out as unqualified graduates. This is an indication that secondary schools appear not to be attaining the goals and objectives for which they are established. It is also an indicator of possibility that the existing management practices by principals is inadequate.

Field visit to some of the federal government secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria revealed that some teachers and non-teaching staff in the zone appear to show little or no

commitment in terms of carrying out their assigned duties. Some of them are more concentrated in organizing private lessons for students from wealthy homes while others engage in other private businesses. There are also cases of indifferent attitude among the staff towards co-curricular activities and other programmes in the schools. There are cases of bullying, lateness to school, destruction of school facilities, immorality and indecent dressing habits among the staff and students alike. In Nigeria, internal examinations are conducted every term while external examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), National Examination Council (NECO), Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) among others are conducted at the end of six years of secondary education. Over the years, discrepancies have been observed in the performance of students in these examination; some perform well while others' performance are nothing to write home about. All these seem to point to the fact that teachers are defective in their job performance. It is against this backdrop, that the study sought to investigate quality management principles as correlates of teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate quality management principles as correlates of teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. In specific terms, the study was intended to:

1. find out the relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
2. determine the relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
3. examine the relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of probability:

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1. There is no significant relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in South-East, Nigeria made up of five states namely Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. The population of the study comprised all the 1,572 teachers in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 472 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique.

The instruments for data collection were structured questionnaires titled: Quality Management Principles Questionnaire, (QMPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire, (JJPQ). QMPQ contained 30 items arranged in five Clusters namely: 1-5. Cluster 1 which centred on focus on learning contained 10 items, Cluster 2 contained 10 items on staff development and Cluster 3 which centred on teamwork contained 10 items. TJPQ contained 20 items which all measure teachers' job performance. The three sets of instruments were structured on a four-point rating of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. Face and construct validation of the instrument were conducted by three experts (two in the area of Educational Management and one in the area of Measurement and Evaluating) all from the Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Copies of the questionnaire together with the research topic, purpose; research questions and hypotheses were given to the experts. They were implored to objectively and constructively examine the appropriateness of wordings and suitability of the instrument to ensure its validity for the study. The experts after assessing the instruments recommended among others that: all the double barreled questions should be expunged and replaced. Construct validity was also conducted by the use of factor analysis with split-sample estimation involving the Varimax Rotation. Total of all factors having eigenvalues higher than 1 were obtained. This is in line with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) criterion of 1. The total percentage variance in the instrument was 343.307% explainable by these factors. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was carried out using a sample of 20 teachers in unity schools in South-South Zone. The Cronbach Alpha Statistics was used to determine the reliability of the instruments. The co-efficient of 0.924, 0.864 and 0.814 were

obtained for the three clusters of QMPQ with the overall reliability index being .867 and the coefficient value obtained for TJPQ was 906 which indicates that the instruments are reliable.

The researcher used direct delivery method to administer copies of the questionnaires to the respondents in their respective schools. Out of the 472 copies distributed, 458 copies indicating 97% return rate were duly filled, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data collected was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and simple regression to test the hypotheses. Pearson (r) simple and multiple regressions were considered ideal for the study, because the study ascertained the extent of relationship between two or more variables in the study. For decision on the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Nworgu (2015) as follows:

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Negligible correlation
.20- .39	Low Correlation
.40- .59	Moderate correlation
.60- .79	Substantial
.80- .1.00	Very high correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05, the null hypotheses was accepted. All analysis was done using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria?

Table 1: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Focus on Learning and Teachers' Job Performance

Variables	N	Focus on Learning	Teachers' Job Performance	Remarks
Focus on Learning	458	1.00	.734	Substantial
Teachers' Job Performance	458	.734	1.00	

As shown in Table 1, a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .458 was obtained. This shows that there is substantial positive relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in focus on learning will lead to substantial improvement on teachers' job performance.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Staff Development and Teachers' Job Performance

Variables	N	Staff Development	Teachers' Job Performance	Remarks
Staff Development	458	1.00	.858	Very High
Teachers' Job Performance	458	.858	1.00	

Table 2 revealed that a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .858 was obtained. This shows that there is very high relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in staff development will contribute to high improvement on teachers' job performance.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between teamwork and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria?

Table 3: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Teamwork and Teachers’ Job Performance

Variables	N	Teamwork	Teachers’ Job Performance	Remarks
Teamwork	458	1.00	.670	Substantial
Teachers’ Job Performance	458	.670	1.00	

Data presented in Table 3, a Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of .670 was obtained. This shows that there is substantial relationship between teamwork and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in teamwork will substantially improve the teachers’ job performance.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between focus on learning process and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 4: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Focus on Learning and Teachers’ Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Focus on Learning Process	.734	.539	532.608	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 4, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .734, while the R² is .539 showing that focus on learning process makes 53.9% contribution to the variance in teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The $F(1/458) = 532.608$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between focus on learning process and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 5: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Staff Development and Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Staff Development	.858	.736	1271.079	.004	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 5, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .858, while the R² is .736 showing that 73.6% improvement on teachers' job performance could be attributed to staff development. The $F(1/458) = 1271.079$ and the p -value of .004 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 6: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Teamwork and Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Teamwork	.670	.448	370.551	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 6, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .670, while the R² is .448 showing that teamwork makes 44.8% contribution to the variance in teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The $F(1/458) = 370.551$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05.

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Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that there is substantial relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The finding is in line with the finding of Llantos and Pamatmat (2016) which showed that focus on learning process substantially relates to teachers' job performance. This refuted the finding of Kaegon's (2008) study which established that focus on learning process principle does not relate to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. The contradiction in the findings could be attributed to difference in geographical locations and wide variation of the time span of the studies. The teachers that focus on learning process engage in quality interaction with the teachers and use varied teaching methods to meet the aspirations of all students which substantially improve their job performance. The focus on learning process ensure that teachers complete their scheme of work at the stipulated time, punctuality to school and commitment to their duties which could explain the substantial relation with their job performance. It was also reported that there is significant relationship between focus on learning process and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The finding is also in tandem with the reports Ebue (2018) and Okone (2019) which established that focus on learning process principle significantly influence teachers; productivity. The agreement in findings could be attributed to the fact that focus on learning process sustain the attention and efforts of teachers in delivering instruction which invariably improve their job performance.

The result of the study indicated that there is very high relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This contradicted the finding of Onyali and Alaeke (2021) who reported that there was moderate relationship between staff professional development practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The possible explanation for the contradiction in findings could be the difference in geographical locations. The staff professional development has very high correlation with teachers' job performance possibly due the fact that it enables them update their skills and broaden their knowledge for effective execution of tasks in the workplace. The technological advance, change and innovation in education institutions necessitated the staff professional development to enable teachers align with changes and use innovative devices to improve their job performance. Staff development prepares teachers for more responsibilities and higher job performance in the schools. It was also found out that there is significant relationship between staff development and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This supported

the finding of Onyali and Alaeke (2021) which indicated that there was significant relationship between staff professional development practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. This agreed with the finding of Kamaldeen, Oluyemisi, Busayo, Abdulrafiu and Laro (2020) who reported that there was a significant relationship between staff professional development and teachers' job performance. The possible explanation for the agreement in findings is that the two studies were conducted in the same country.

The finding of the study revealed that there is substantial relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This affirmed the finding of Hwang (2018) who indicated that there was substantial relationship between teamwork and team performance. This is in line with the finding of Agwu (2015) who reported that there exists substantial relationship between teamwork and employees' job performance. The agreement between the studies could be due to the fact that they are conducted in the same country and zone. The teamwork promotes the exchange of ideas which make teachers work more efficient and thereby lead to substantially improvement on their job performance. Teamwork creates group cohesion and enjoyable work environment that leads to higher job performance. Through the teamwork principles, new teachers can learn from the experience and expertise of their senior colleagues, while the more experienced teachers get fresh ideas from new ones which substantially improve their job performance. It was also revealed that there is significant relationship between teamwork and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This agreed with the finding of Hwang (2018) who indicated that there was significant relationship between teamwork and team performance. This affirmed the finding of Agwu (2015) who reported that significant relationship exists between teamwork and employees' job performance. The possible reason for the result is that teamwork encourage support and exchange of ideas that boost morale of teachers and significantly improve their job performance.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that there is very high positive correlation between quality management principles and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The quality management principles set fundamental rules and standard for operating school activities to promote the job performance of teachers. Quality management principles contribute the conformance to requirements of various aspects of teaching profession, support and coordination of the available resources to bring high improvement on the job performance of teachers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the results of the study:

1. Unity school principals should constitute committee saddled with the responsibility of monitoring and ensuring constantly focus on learning process to improve the job performance of teachers.
2. Federal Ministry of Education should organize an annual intensive staff professional development programmes to enable teachers update their skills and knowledge for improvement on their job performance.
3. Principals should promote teamwork environment by delegating tasks to group of teachers with commensurate authority which promote exchange of ideas and expertise that enhance teachers' job performance.

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